

Did Dr. B.R. Ambedkar Promote Women's Rights In The Family Space?

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Abstract

The views and actions of Dr. B.R. Ambedkar are well known regarding the caste system in India. However, through this paper, the researcher aims to understand whether he played a role in the emancipation of women in the familial space from gender-based oppression, as promulgated by various Brahmanical texts like the Manusmriti. It was found that through his writings and speeches such as "Castes in India: Their Mechanism, Genesis, and Development", "The Riddle of Women", and most importantly his efforts in the formation of the Hindu Code Bill, he was a firm supporter of women rights in the private sphere, as well.

In conclusion, Ambedkar believed that the caste system in India, in especially the prominence of the Brahmins (the highest caste), continued to oppress women. He held the Brahminical patriarchal system to blame for the oppression of women in Indian society. Ambedkar contended that the caste system and the submissive status of women within it were maintained by the Brahmins' patriarchal culture. He thought that Brahmins had created complex rites and customs that prevented women from fully participating in social and religious life and criticised Brahminical practises that disadvantaged women, such as child marriage, dowries, and the seclusion of women in the home, in his writings and speeches. Most notably, his involvement in the creation of the Hindu Code Bill demonstrated his steadfast support for women's rights in the private sphere.

Keywords: Ambedkar, women's rights, India, caste system, Manusmriti, Hinduism, oppression, Brahmins, Hindu Code Bill

Introduction

The Position of Women's Rights in India Before Ambedkar

The national imaginary has been largely shaped by the image of the lady. The same is true of India. Women are frequently portrayed as societal and national cultural icons of India. She is swiftly denounced as a menace to culture and tradition because of changes to her appearance and behaviour (Rege, 2013). These reactions have been seen all across the world. These can initially be interpreted as responses typical of patriarchal societies. These essentially patriarchal responses need to be coupled with unique colonial societies', in this case India's historical experiences on a deeper level. Changes to "tradition" had to be rejected on the grounds that they were foreign and Western and that they went against "natural" patriarchal standards.

Depending on caste, class, age, and religious group, literature on religion, law, politics, and education contained distinct pronouncements for males. In contrast, the biological traits of women and the supportive, subservient roles they were meant to perform hid their distinctions. The way historians portrayed Indian women was also essentialist.

The narratives occasionally singled out one woman for extra attention, but most often this was because of how impressive by male standards her efforts were. Geraldine Forbes also stated that concerns relating to women's life, such as household and agricultural technologies, religious rites and sentiments, fertility and family size, furniture, jewels, and apparel, inheritance and property rights, marriage and divorce, were largely overlooked (Forbes, 2003). Virginia Woolf made the following observation about history written from a woman's perspective regarding the ironic paradox of a woman's life: Though practically she is absolutely unimportant, conceptually she is of the utmost importance. She permeates every page of poetry. She virtually disappears from history (Woolf, 1900).

The caste system, which served as Hinduism's social foundation, began to be called into question over time as structured reform parties like the Brahmo Samaj, Arya Samaj, Satyashodhak Samaj, and others grew in number. Numerous social service organisations took up the cause of the socially disadvantaged and worked to free India from the tyranny of caste. Hinduism's social and religious reform movements in the nineteenth century opposed societal and judicial injustices (Chakravarty, 2003). These movements' main goal was the abolition of caste and gender discrimination in society. It involved an attack on social practises and institutions that had their roots in many theological traditions, such as child marriage, the status and treatment of widows, isolation, and the denial of women's rights to property and education. However, the primary "object" of reform and the centre of the social reform movements' discourse was the upper caste/upper class woman (Chakravarty, 2003). Hence, even though gender based discrimination began to be recognized and denounced, the women these protests were for, were limited.

In the contents that follow, the researcher aims to deconstruct several significant works by Dr. B.R. Ambedkar to understand his mindset and whether he initiated efforts towards improving the condition of women in India, including Dalit women, specifically in the familial space.

Castes in India: Their Mechanism, Genesis, and Development

Ambedkar provides a groundbreaking account of endogamy and the ensuing violation of women's rights as a method of maintaining it in "Castes in India," which is a landmark work (Krishnamurthy, 2022).

In this paper read by Ambedkar in New York in 1916, he expressed how he thought that the only characteristic of caste was endogamy. Castes in India, in Ambedkar's words, "mean an artificial chopping off of the population into fixed and definite units, each of which is prevented from fusing into one another through the practise of endogamy". He contends that demonstrating the operation of endogamy will demonstrate its genesis and mechanism. He stated that endogamy was previously unfamiliar to India in this context. He supports this truth by demonstrating the

Sagotra marriage restriction practise. He asserted that exogamy prevented caste since it results in fusion" (Rege, 2013).

Ambedkar used an imagined group that wishes to become a caste to illustrate how endogamy generally functions. He then looked at the strategies they used to uphold endogamy. Caste must be maintained by enclosing a circle. (Rege, 2013). But because there is typically "only enough sex between those of the same age" in any community, this presents an internal issue with maintaining equality between the sexes. The ultimate purpose, according to Ambedkar, is to correct this inequity, hence this conjugal right must be granted. "The couple dying at the same time, which is a rare contingency, is the only way the much-needed parity is realised."

Ambedkar now introduces the ideas of the surplus man and woman. He believes that they both pose a threat to the caste system and must be eliminated (Rege, 2013). First, dispose of the surplus woman by burning her on her late husband's funeral pyre. However, this approach to addressing the issue of sex disparity is fairly unworkable. It might work in some situations and might not in others. As a result, it is impossible to get rid of every surplus woman because doing so would be a simple answer but a difficult realisation. So, if not removed, the surplus woman (= widow) stays with the community, yet her very presence poses a twofold threat. She may leave the caste and engage in exogamy, or she could marry within the caste and through competition encroach upon the chances of marriage that must be reserved for the potential brides in the caste. If she cannot be burned with her late husband, she is consequently a threat and needs to be dealt with. The second solution is to make her live as a widow for the rest of her days. Burning is a better option than imposing widowhood in terms of the objective outcomes. Burning the widow puts an end to all three dangers that a surplus lady carries. She poses no issues for remarriage either within or beyond the caste because she is dead and gone. However, forced widowhood is preferable to burning since it is more realistic (Rege, 2003).

He then spoke about the challenging situation of the surplus man. He demonstrated how patriarchal society is to demonstrate his point. Ambedkar emphasised that in such a scenario, man cannot be burned. The alternative method is to compel celibacy and make the person a widower for life. However, given human nature, this is challenging to do and, even if it does, it would be against the caste's interests because the caste wants the men to be "Grihastha." The only option left is to give him a wife who isn't yet ready for marriage. Even if requiring celibacy and lifetime widowhood is problematic, they have nonetheless been used as a tool. When all of these methods are combined, they produce endogamy, which is the result, in Ambedkar's opinion. He looked for ways to maintain the "sacred notion" of endogamy that Hindus would have followed. He discovered three rituals in this context: Sati, forced widowhood, girl marriage, and occasionally Sannyasa for a widower (Barnwal, 2014).

Ambedkar claims that despite the fact that there are a few ideologies in its honour, there is no scientific basis for these traditions. He explained 'sati' using the the A.K. Coomaraswamy school of thought, which supports it as a wife's "devotion beyond the grave." No one would have supported forced widowhood, but many people still followed it, according to Ambedkar. Then he discussed Ketkar's justification for child marriage: A faithful man or woman ought not to feel affection for a woman or man other than the one with whom he is in a committed relationship.

This according to him should be followed even before marriage. This perception results in girl-child marriage. Ambedkar thinks that these were honored because they were practiced. He said that it's the initiative of custom which is important and the philosophy will justify it. These philosophies are "to gild the pill". Though represented as ideals, their real nature is but a means to maintain endogamy (Ambedkar, 1951).

The researcher, after examining the aforementioned paper, believes that Ambedkar was setting the groundwork for what was, strictly speaking, a feminism-based view of caste by framing it in terms of gender distinctions that dictated the worth of surplus man and surplus woman in the familial sphere. We discover that there are two ways in which the surplus lady gets "disposed of". When sati—the burning of a woman on her husband's pyre—could not be accomplished, forced and demeaning widowhood was employed. None of these, according to Ambedkar, were considered appropriate to be applied to the surplus man, however, clearly sending a message of a woman's supposed "inferiority" in front of a man, and how that meant she was lesser deserving, if deserving at all, of basic human rights. "Male superiority among groups" required treating a surplus man or widower differently. Because losing a man meant losing work and reducing the size of the group, the issue was solved by marrying him to a member of a group that wasn't yet eligible for marriage, and a moral divide was crossed by institutionalising female child marriage. Ambedkar asserts that researchers have spent more time analysing how sati, child marriage, and forced widowhood accumulated societal value than looking into the causes of endogamy. He is undoubtedly underlining a dual strategy used by Brahmanical ideology to uphold and glorify the very practises that denigrated women in this passage. Three operations that are crucial to the emergence and growth of caste are highlighted in Ambedkar's formulation: intra-group reproductive planning, the violent control of surplus women's sexuality, and the justification of control measures through ideology.

Riddles in Hinduism & The Riddle of Women

One of Ambedkar's numerous publications that was never published while he was alive was "Riddles in Hinduism". By the end of November 1955, he had finished the book that he had begun in the first week of January 1954. The Shiv Sena requested a ban on the publication of this book by the Maharashtra government in 1987, but it was released under the title BAWS Volume 4 and included twenty-four riddles and eight appendices (Kalyani, 2022).

Ambedkar claimed that the writings on Hinduism written by Brahmin authors lacked rational thought, whereas "Riddles in Hinduism" appealed to the intellectual half of the Hindu mind. In order to encourage the reader to reflect for themselves, Ambedkar closes each chapter with riddles, acknowledging that Hindus are capable of rational thought (Kawade, 2021). The text that has survived has more than 170,000 words. It includes a number of Ambedkar's incomplete notes and chapters with blank text. It has 24 "riddles" and 8 appendices that are divided into religious, social, and political categories.

Ambedkar's justification for why violence against women in a Brahmanical patriarchal culture is graded in nature is given in three riddles about what he refers to as the "Madness of Manu". In Riddle No. 19, Ambedkar's claim that Hindu Law recognised eight forms of marriage and

thirteen kinds of sons, prepares the ground for his subsequent criticism of multiple marital forms only being "euphemisms for rape and seduction." An examination of this critique put forward by Ambedkar brings to light his belief that Brahminical patriarchy was essentially normalizing sexual assault against women, blanketed as "recognized forms of marriage", and in a larger context, reducing women to entities undeserving of basic human rights in the private space. Riddle 24, or "The Riddle of Rama and Krishna," which Ambedkar had subtitled "An Exposition to Enlighten the Masses,"—is feminist in its slant not only because of the protests and counter-protests it sparked but also because of the centrality of gender in Ambedkar's moral critique of Rama and Krishna and the discussion it sparks for feminist historical interpretations of epic literature. (Rege, 2013). According to this text, Rama was not monogamous, contrary to his good reputation, and his marriage was far from perfect in Ambedkar's interpretation. Notably, after slaying Ravana, Rama acts irresponsibly towards Sita by putting off his visit and, when he does meet her, he ends up questioning her chastity, indicating that his fight with Ravana was motivated more by his own dignity than by the need to save his wife. In reaction, Sita calls Rama 'lowly' before starting a trial by fire. Rama brought Sita back to his capital city of Ayodhya after she passed the fire test to establish her virginity. Rama was personally convinced of Sita's chastity, but when she became pregnant, he abandoned her due to rumours that she was carrying Ravana's child. Rama was a 'cowardly' and 'weak king' who worried more about his reputation and fame than about acting honourably as a husband, despite Hindus using this story to represent him as a democratic king who cared for the public opinion, in Ambedkar's views (Rege, 2013). Demanding Sita to demonstrate her innocence once more highlights her tragedy and Rama's related wrongdoing.

Ambedkar's interpretation of Rama's treatment of Sita brings to light his condemnation of a husband being more concerned with his wife's potential loss of virginity than her being held hostage and being sexually assaulted. Further, it also makes apparent his disagreement with a man "discarding" his pregnant wife, simply to protect his own reputation. Ambedkar also was against the objectification of women and worship of a God despite his promiscuousness, which in a Goddess would most definitely be highly condemned, and would also prevent the title of "goddess" being awarded to her in the first place. The researcher holds this opinion based on their study of the "Riddle of Krishna", where Ambedkar describes women as the objects of Krishna's delight. He does this by citing examples of obscenity like *vastra-harana* (Krishna snatching the gopis' garments), which the Brahmanic texts themselves admit they would have condemned if they weren't mythical. Further, the Riddle also mentions that Krishna had 16,108 consorts inherited from the harem of a fallen king, eight major wives won in battle or taken away from Swayamvara marriages, and how it would not be wrong to term Krishna as almost pathologically promiscuous.

Two copies of Ambedkar's unpublished essay, which was later published posthumously in Volume 3 under the title "The Woman and Counter-Revolution." were also discovered. In a different copy, the essay was entitled "The Riddle of Women". The essay begins with a statement: 'Manu can hardly be said to be more tender to women than he was to the Shudra.' It ends with a riddle: 'In short, in pre-Manu days a woman was [a] free and equal partner of man. Why did Manu degrade her?' (Ambedkar, 1987). Ambedkar illustrates Manu's negative view on women with numerous quotations from the original work, focusing on his observation that

“women's natural seduction of men leads to vice and disloyalty and calls for the need for control”. Ambedkar goes on to then present the opposite picture of the author of the Manusmriti as a misogynist, whose law of divorce neither curbed a man from giving up his wife nor preempted him from abandoning or selling her, which then programmatically thwarted the wife from seeking her own freedom. Manu's injunction is frequently explained as having sacralized marriage. Justice and injustice, according to Ambedkar, were irrelevant to Manu precisely because the moral politics that defined those concepts were twisted. The law's many tricks relegated a wife to the status of a slave in terms of property and barred her from studying Vedas and belonging to heretical groups in an effort to diminish the freedom women had previously enjoyed during the Buddhist era. Ambedkar ends by outlining the ideal existence Manu envisioned for women, one in which she would revere her husband despite all of his shortcomings.

Ambedkar's criticism of Manu's regulations for Hindu women, while appearing to be an attack, is actually a careful comparison with a pre-Manu Hindu order. In order to achieve this, he heavily references Kautilya's Arthashastra, emphasizing the prospects for women to engage in intellectual debate with men, their participation in royal coronations, the prevalence of post-puberty marriages and the ideal of monogamy, the availability of divorce, the absence of a prohibition on widow remarriage, the provision of a wife's endowment and maintenance, and even the potential to sue a husband for assault and defamation (Chakravarty, 2003). Ambedkar uses an interrogatory tone primarily when defining the Manu's law model, which shows how marriage, kinship, and the devaluation of women are fundamentally linked to the reproduction of graded inequality in society. He specifically poses three questions that are connected, namely:

1. Why did Manu say that some castes were bastard castes/of mixed origin when as a matter of fact they were independent in their existence?
2. Why did Manu, going against the basic assumption of patriarchal society, change the law from Pitra-savarnaya to Matra-savarnaya?
3. Why did he degrade women?

According to Ambedkar, Manu's strategy is effective because it incites moral worry about women's sexuality and distorts groups that opposed caste dominance. He presented very harsh criticism of Manu's handling of women and believed that Manu was to blame for the unfortunate patriarchal attitudes and gender inequality that pervaded Indian society. Ambedkar had also talked extensively about the part played by Manu in the repression of women in his book "The Untouchables: Who Were They and Why They Became Untouchables?". He claimed that the Manusmriti was a sexist literature that justified women's enslavement and deprives them of fundamental human rights. A study of “The Riddle of Women” brings to our awareness Ambedkar’s denunciation of treatment of women as slaves in the house, bounded by utmost control from birth till death. It leads the researcher to believe he was dissatisfied with the idea of a society devoid of monogamy, the predominance of post-pubescent marriages, the opportunity to divorce, the lack of a ban on widow remarriage, and the supply of a wife's endowment and

maintenance. The final question posed by Ambedkar in this text, i.e. "Why did he degrade women" leaves no doubt in the mind about Ambedkar's views on women's rights.

The Hindu Code Bill

Jawaharlal Nehru established a subcommittee in 1948, and Ambedkar was chosen as its chairman with the task of drafting the Hindu Code Bill. The Bill attempted to define the various property rights and institutions that apply to men and women, change the succession order, and create new rules for minorities, marriage, divorce, adoption, and child support. Ambedkar raised previously unheard-of issues in the formation of this Bill, including the elimination of the birthright to property, property by survivorship, the half-share for daughters, the transformation of women's limited estate into an absolute estate, the elimination of caste in marriage and adoption, and the monogamy and divorce principles (Moon, 1979). Even a cursory glance reveals that the intended legal reforms sought to curtail and regulate behaviours that perpetuated Brahmanical patriarchy. These included the threat that polygamy posed to women, forced endogamy, the lack of an absolute right to property for women, the indissolubility of marriage for women, and others. The Hindu Mahasabha, other Hindu religious leaders, and Congress legislators all bitterly opposed the Bill, which challenged the basic foundation of Brahmanical patriarchy. Due to the drastic divergence from traditional Hindu philosophy, the Bill was not conceded but rather withdrawn in the face of opposition from Hindu Orthodoxy, especially from the Manuwadi-honoring Hindu Mahasabha and Bharatiya Janata Sangh. "The Hindu Mahasabha opposed the Bill in order to prevent any legislative interference in the religious matters in Hindus and it has been stated that it is against the 'Indian culture' as it provides the options of divorce, and monogamy that may prevent a man to have son i.e. sacrosanct for salvation and etc". The bill's clauses regarding "women's property rights, monogamy, and divorce" had received intense opposition from these religious, conservative, and patriarchal social elements (Rege, 2013).

Ambedkar, in an attempt to quell the protests by the aforementioned groups, emphasised that Brahmanic codes never declared unrestricted polygamy to be the law. Monogamy was in fact preferred over polygamy, which was only advised in specific circumstances. Further, he expressed his personal support for monogamy, and to prove that this was a principle shared by pan-cultural contemporary governments, cited laws from princely kingdoms and other nations. He went on to question, the imposition of minority rule on the majority because divorce was a common practise or legislation among Shudras, who made up 90% of Indian culture. In order to show that strict closures in marriage practises (the Brahmanization of the practises), if they existed at all, were a later addition, he drew on Kautilya's political treatise Arthashastra. In essence, Hindu law makers' agreement was much less total than is generally believed. He then addressed the topic of women's property, or stridhan, which is a major topic in the smritis. He began by criticising the ancient Brahmans for making the formulation of the smritis their main work in a typically hilarious way. He ranked the debate over women's property as one of the most complex and nuanced because there were at least 137 different opinions expressed in the smritis on stridhan (Cousins, 1947). Ambedkar distinguished between stridhan gained prior to and following marriage, as well as between widow's property and a daughter's portion. He addressed objections to women receiving absolute inheritance as opposed to restricted estate. He also specifically disputed the idea that women are naïve and ignorant, and that they are more

prone to manage and transfer property in ways that are bad for them and their family (Moon, 1979). Ambedkar further challenged his detractors to provide evidence as to why women who could be trusted to dispose of stridhan, were insufficiently trustworthy to handle widow property and answer why shouldn't they acquire absolute property rights? He asserted that there were various grounds for supporting the daughter's claim to her part of the property. On a more advanced level, one could argue against Hindu society's predilection for sons. By only repeating the part given to the daughter by the two Smritikaras, Manu and Yagnavalkya, he made it clear that he was putting out a lower level of logic.

Further, women's life were frequently put in the hands of Hindu male interpreters because there was no true codification or standardisation. "Mitakshra" and "Dayabhaga," are the two rules in Hinduism that govern inheritance, marriage, adoption, and other matters. According to Mitakshra rule of law, a man's property does not belong to him personally; rather, it is shared by all male lineage members, including his father, son, grandson, and great-grandson, from the moment of their birth. The ownership of property has a distinct character under Dayabhaga law, meaning that anyone who inherits property from their ancestors has unrestricted control over it. Ambedkar used this latter branch of the law in the Hindu Code Bill, and by adapting it to contemporary demands, it was intended to become common law (Ambedkar, 1989). There was prejudice against female heirs, however, even by Dayabhaga, based on whether or not they were married and whether or not they had children. The Hindu Code Bill included other proposals to eliminate this prejudice. Ambedkar equalised the status of widows, daughters, and widows of departed sons. The daughter's portion in her father's and her husband's estate was mandated to be equal to the son's share in order to reestablish gender balance. She was given the same inheritance rights as the son, widow, predeceased son's widow, predeceased son's son, and predeceased son's widow's predeceased son. It is noteworthy that Ambedkar established complete equality between son and daughter by declaring that "son also would get a share as equal to girl's share in mother's property, even in Stridhana" (described in Hindu Law as riches received by women as presents from relatives) (Ambedkar, 1989). Further, women were to be given complete property rights as a result of the Bill. Under Dayabhaga law, women had only the right to a "life estate," or property that they could use for as long as they wanted to, but they were not allowed to sell it under any circumstances. Ambedkar made a revolutionary change in this area as well, insisting on converting this partly land into an absolute estate that a lady might use anyway she saw fit (Singariya, 2014), and ensuring that this land would transfer to a member of her husband's family after she passed away. A further unbreakable rule governing women's property was that an adopted son would not be able to evict the woman from any property she had received from her late husband before the adoption of the son. As a result, when the bill was approved, "widows' positions were strengthened because an adopted son or step-son would not be in a position to divest the mother completely from her property." Ambedkar further stipulates in the bill that the dowry provided to the daughter by her parents at the time of her marriage must be recognised as her own property by her in-laws in accordance with Stridhana, which is defined in Hindu Law as riches obtained by women as gifts from relatives (More, 2014).

However, there was still ferocious opposition from all sides. One of the President's threats was to prevent the Bill from becoming law. Parliament was under siege by Hindu sadhus, landowners and business organisations issued a warning about pulling out of next elections. As a result, we can draw the conclusion that the Hindu Code Bill presented an immediate danger to the pre-existing patriarchal systems in India, by allowing women's access to and control over resources and property, the potential for the abolition of caste-based limitations on marriage and adoption, and the emergence of the right to divorce. The institutional ties between caste, kinship, and property that form the very foundation of Brahmanical patriarchy appeared to be intimidated by all of this (Moon, 1979). Reactions to the Bill are best defined by the potential it had for upending long-standing patriarchal and caste constraints over reproduction and production processes. The growing social validity of male promiscuity and the declining sexual vulnerability of women in the Brahmanical order were both threatened by the bill (Sinha, 1988). The bill itself represented a significant escape from Hinduism and its oppressive gender rules.

The accompanying picture of the key elements of the Hindu Code make it quite clear that Ambedkar reframed the legislation with his ardour for the ideals of liberty, equality, fraternity, and dignity, which he believed women were equally deserving of. He felt that the restoration of these social democratic ideals would come about through the seamless entanglement of the overture of the women's absolute share in property, a purging of caste restrictions in issues of marriage and adoption, eradication of polygamy, and overture of monogamy, or essentially, giving women equal status as men in the private sphere. As a result, the Bill attacked Hinduism's core beliefs by opposing the system of male dominance and female subjugation. The Hindu Code Bill was finally passed in 1955–1966, during Ambedkar's absence from the cabinet, though in a watered-down form and as four separate laws, namely the Hindu Marriage Act of 1955, the Hindu Succession Act of 1956, the Hindu Adoption and Maintenance Act of 1956, and the Hindu Minority and Guardianship Act of 1956.

Conclusion

The aforementioned speeches & writings by Dr. Ambedkar and their subsequent analysis by the researcher leads to the conclusion that women's empowerment in the familial space was not ignored by Ambedkar. Ambedkar was of the opinion that women were mistreated by India's caste system, which was dominated by the Brahmins (the highest caste), and believed it was to blame for the oppression of women in Indian society. He argued that the patriarchal culture of the Brahmins was what kept the caste system in place, as well as the women's subordinate standing within it, and was strongly in favour of emancipating women and freeing them from oppressive Brahmanical practices such as that of sati, dowry, child marriage, endogamy, etc, and also equally wanted to ensure divorce, property, inheritance, and guardianship rights for women that were egalitarian and just, to ensure women enjoyed a status equal to that of man in the home.

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